

Spiritual Intelligence among Women B.Ed. Students in Madurai District

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Abstract

Even though humanity has reached the age of wisdom, many cultures of today are still characterized as “left-brained”, material or “spiritually stunted”. Due to these problems in the fabric of daily life, quite a number of people are making an effort to find ways to re-connect with their essence, attain a higher meaning in life, manage uncertainties successfully with inner poise, and in short to undergo an “inner change”.

A higher level of intelligence power distinguishes human beings from other animals on this planet. It has been the favourite subject of research for psychologists. In the 20th century, they created IQ tests to define and measure intelligence power of an individual. But, it proved inadequate for measuring the wide spectrum of intelligence. In the 21st century, they are saying that ultimate intelligence is spiritual intelligence.

Developing spiritual intelligence includes and transcends personal growth, extending to the farther reaches of healthy psychological development. Some personal characteristics that could be associated with spiritual intelligence are the traditional virtues of veracity, humility, and charity, which could also be described as authenticity, respect for differences, and the willingness to engage in service to others. One of the qualities of SQ is wisdom. This includes knowing the limits of our knowledge. Other ingredients are values such as courage, integrity, intuition, and compassion (Parthasarathy, 2007: 149-150).

Need for the Study

Today the field of psychology has shown the tendency towards the spiritual dimensions and wide horizons for extended research has spread that can reflect the profound influence of spiritual forces on the human body and mind and makes clear the importance of spiritual intelligence. Spiritual approaches to health and sciences, for researchers and mental health professionals have recently been emphasized. Mental health professionals have recognized the power of spiritual intelligence, some of which are defined as capacity to feel,

understand and present the highest part of themselves, others and the world around. Spirituality is derived from the Latin word “Spirare” meaning to breathe. Spirituality is inherent aspect of human nature and essence of our existence so it draws attention of many theorists as the source of all thoughts, feelings, values and behaviour. Variations of spiritual intelligence are sometimes used in corporate settings, as a means of motivating employees. According to Stephen Covey, “Spiritual intelligence is the central and most fundamental of all the intelligences, because it becomes the source of guidance for the others” Spiritual Intelligence (SQ). According to Webster’s dictionary the word “Spirit” defines as “the animating or vital principle: that which gives life to the physical organism in contrast to its material elements: the breath of life”. So spiritual intelligence positive influence in teacher education. Therefore, this research is necessary to know the B.Ed. women students having spiritual intelligence. Hence, the need for the study.

Terms and Definitions

Spiritual intelligence: refers to the holistic concept in incorporating mind, body and spirit. It is the intelligence with which persons address and solve problems with meaning and other values of life.

B.Ed. Women students: refers to those who are studying Ist and IInd year undergraduate education degree in Madurai District.

Variables of the Study

Dependent Variable

1. Spiritual intelligence

Independent Variables

1. Gender: Male / Female
2. Religion: Hindu / Others
3. Family Type: Joint / Nuclear
4. Family Kind: orthodox / Modern

Objectives of the Study

To specify objectives of the present study are listed below:

1. To measure the level of spiritual intelligence among B.Ed. students in Madurai District.
2. To find out whether there is significant difference in spiritual intelligence among B.Ed. women students in terms of select independent variables viz. Gender, Religion, Family type and Family kind.

Hyporthesis of the Study

Each of the independent variables involved in this study exerts a significant difference in the spiritual intelligence among B.Ed. students.

Methodology in Brief

Method: Normative; Technique: Survey;

Sample: A stratified representative sample of 364 B.Ed. women Students from seven colleges of education from Madurai district with due representation given to select independent variables.

Tools Used

1. “Spiritual Intelligence Inventory” Constructed and Standardized by Leka. V. (2015).
2. General Information Sheet.

Statistical Treatment

t- test for significance of difference between the means of large independent samples.

Analysis and Discussions

Spiritual Intelligence Among B.ed. Women Students In Madurai District

The average score of spiritual intelligence among B.Ed. women students is found to be 36.59 while the theoretical average is 25 only. Hence spiritual intelligence of B.Ed. women students is found to be a above the average level. In other words, Spiritual Intelligence among B.Ed. women students is found to be satisfactory.

Hypotheses Verifications

The statistical measures and the results of test of significance of difference between the mean scores of spiritual intelligence among B.Ed. women students with respect to independent variables are presented in Table 1.

Variable	Sub-Variables	N	M	SD	‘t’ Value	Significance At 0.05 Level
Gender	Male	58	36.55	4.12	-0.112	Not significant
	Female	306	36.62	4.46		
Religion	Hindu	292	36.40	4.61	-2.198	significant
	Others	72	37.44	3.32		
Family Type	Orthodox	131	36.95	3.97	1.123	Not significant
	Modern	233	36.42	4.63		
Family Kind	Joint	221	36.70	4.31	0.501	Not significant
	Nuclear	143	36.46	4.56		

Spiritual Intelligence and Gender

The obtained ‘t’ value -0.112 is found lesser than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is no significant difference between male and female students in their possession of spiritual intelligence. Hence the hypothesis is rejected.

Spiritual Intelligence and Religion

The obtained ‘t’ value -2.198 is found higher than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is a significant difference between male and female students in their possession of spiritual intelligence. Hence the hypothesis is accepted.

Spiritual Intelligence and Family type

The obtained ‘t’ value -1.123 is found lesser than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is no significant difference between orthodox and modern family type students in their possession of spiritual intelligence. Hence the hypothesis is rejected.

Spiritual Intelligence and Family kind

The obtained 't' value 0.501 is found lesser than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is no significant difference between joint and nuclear family kind students in their possession of spiritual intelligence. Hence the hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusions

The major conclusions emerged out of the present study are presented below:

1. Spiritual Intelligence among B.Ed., students are found to be well above the average.
2. Spiritual intelligence level is found independent upon Gender, Family Type and Family Kind.
3. Spiritual intelligence level is found dependent on Religion.

Educational Implications

Spiritual intelligence has become an important part of our lives as well as workplace. Spirituality is considered as one of the key factors for the success of the educational organizations and ultimately for the professional life of the teacher. The spiritual perspective is causing shift in the workplace values promoting cooperation rather than fear at the work place. Spirituality in the workplace as a framework proves the role of organizational values in a culture and the role of spirituality is important in creating and instilling values and culture in an organization. When people have high spirituality in the workplace, it may be more responsible for the organization and they have a high loyalty. Spiritual intelligence, using a multisensory approach to access one's inner knowledge to solve global problems, could be an integrating theme to create global awareness among teachers and students.

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